

THE RELATIONSHIPS OF FORMING LIFE CONTENT AND CREATIVE THINKING OF MILITARY SERVANTS

Umarov Ismoiljon Olimjonovich¹

Faculty of Military Education teacher
reserve lieutenant colonel

¹Fagana State University

Ergashev Shahrukhkhan Muzaffar ugli²

Salimov Javohir Abdumomin ugli³

Students of Military education of

²⁻³Fergana State University

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Abstract: This article reveals the relationship between the life content of military personnel and the formation of creative thinking . It shows the improvement of development by increasing the number of professionals who can be creative in every modern, demanding field . Important points were put forward in the formation of creative thinking in military personnel.

Key words : creativity, creative thinking, modernity, science, tactical thinking, creativity in language.

Abstract: This article reveals interrelationships between the life content of servicemen and the formation of creative thinking. It shows improvement in development by increasing the number of professionals who can be creative in every field, meeting modern requirements . Important points were put forward in the formation of creative thinking among servicemen.

"The country that relies on a new idea, a new idea, and innovation will win. If we start building our great future from today, it should be started on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach."

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev

Introduction: The question of the meaning of life appears before each person in one form or another with varying degrees of tension and difficulty . Filling one 's life with content is a characteristic of the number . He tends to have a purpose in which his life activities are directed . A person who realizes that he is not eternal, that he will die, wants to know some kind of eternity and seeks his own place in society . He tries to increase the value of his life . Considering a person's development as a goal of social development , it allows to compare the interests of the individual and the interests of the development of the society on a humane, spiritual basis . This methodical reasoning requires searching for the meaning of life in the traces of human life, in the constant development and improvement of the creative possibilities of the individual. Therefore, AMKorshunov said, "Creation is the active interaction of the subject with the object . " In this process, the subject changes the environment in a goal - oriented manner and creates a new world of social significance according to the objective laws . By influencing the environment, the subject changes itself " [1 . 383-b], - writes.

Literature analysis and methods. The methods of logicity, historicity, consistency and objectivity of scientific knowledge were widely used in the research process. In this article, John Locke's political-philosophical views on state administration and its features today were analyzed. Sh. Tilavoldiyev's book "Bases of military patriotic education" was designated as a methodological resource . At the same time, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's works were widely used.

Discussion and results. Scientific understanding of the meaning of life should also consist of developing a strategy that can lead to results of objective value for human society . In modern conditions, new requirements are placed on military specialists . Because they are often tasked with solving non-standard tasks to ensure the implementation of new ideas . This process is characterized by curiosity, unique enthusiasm , ability to take risks, sensitivity to new ideas and originality of thinking in military specialists . In order to cultivate such creative qualities in military personnel and to increase the effectiveness of the educational process in general , it is necessary to pay special attention to the following: 1) development of creative thinking in the future military specialist ; 2) to achieve the motivation of the educational process that formed the natural-scientific worldview in young military personnel . Today, a cadet who studies a certain science , often cannot adequately imagine its practical importance and its ideological role . Therefore, the formation of a natural-scientific worldview in cadets allows to correctly solve serious problems that arise not only in highly specialized areas in the future , but also constantly . This approach is related to the issue of combat training . In relation to military service, clarifying the scientific understanding of the meaning of human life, the meaning of an officer's life is spiritual, conscious, professional and physical self - improvement, his personal incomparability , peace on earth, prevention of aggression, the peaceful work of the people reliably with weapons. It can be said that life, service path in terms of providing protection consists of the unity of capacities and creative possibilities at each stage. The meaning of an officer's life, no matter how different the district is , can not be different from the meaning of an ordinary citizen . The uniqueness of military service requires a person to undergo continuous military-technical improvement, mental and physical training , and to endure the constant pressure of hard work . At the same time, independence, creativity, the need not to stick to the same pattern when making decisions, regular work with people allows to show and realize the personal incomparability of the officer. However, as the head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoev noted, "At the same time, it is worth saying that, despite the measures taken, the system of training military personnel does not fully meet the requirements of the time . We have not created modern conditions in military schools . On the contrary, our cadets and listeners should have the most advanced , innovative knowledge and skills in the field of education . This is our main goal "[2]. The conditions of military service "condense" the time of spiritual, professional and military recovery of a person as much as possible . In this way, it accelerates the process of realizing its hidden potential . In addition, he shows himself as a person in every moment of everyday life: in the family, on the sports field, in the theater and in other places . He, like any other profession, has universal values of experience. First of all, this is an opportunity to enjoy works of art, to gain spiritual awareness of the world around us. Thus, life values (creativity, creativity, experiences, relationships) constitute the meaning of the officer's life content. The mentioned peculiarities of his profession indicate that there are objective opportunities to have the meaning of life in military service . In the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it takes a special place in the study and implementation of new creative laws of training and education of military personnel with a creative mindset, and in the training of officers . Therefore, creative thinking has a number of dialectical features. Creative thinking is an important factor that increases the fundamental principles and laws of military creative research , the scientific potential of military personnel and military teams. The unique feature of creative thinking is that it serves to solve real creative-combat tasks in military personnel. Solving the tasks of

raising creative thinking in a timely manner allows, first of all, to search for new ways and means of activating the human factor in the interests of strengthening the combat power of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan . Formation of modern scientific and creative thinking among commanders, quality performance of functional and educational tasks , establishment of law, law and order and military discipline in the military community , a unique creative environment, solidarity, mutual demand and personal responsibility. creates the environment.

Creativity in solving creative thinking problems is a special issue that allows to increase the effectiveness of military vocational education. This process includes the following several steps :

1) creative training; 2) creative awareness; 3) incubation period; 4) creative height.

All of these creative stages can be effectively applied in any field of professional activity , as this stage always prioritizes timely problem solving. Thus, the development of a creative algorithm for future independent scientific research in any field of activity of a young military specialist occupies an important place. These stages are as follows: Training. This is the creative planning stage. It collects theoretical information , clearly formulates the problem, and develops scientific and creative predictions about the research results . At this stage, clear rational goals are defined and results are defined. Also, the right direction of research is chosen , the availability of the necessary tools is checked, and an experimental strategy is developed.

In conclusion, it can be said that the low level of development of creative thinking, imagination, and curiosity indicates that this military education system preserves the priority of informing the individual over his culture and the rational aspect over his emotional side. That is, the activities within this educational system are mainly focused on imparting knowledge to cadets , and the educational process itself is based on didactic-centric technology, and the subject-subject relationship between the teacher and the cadet prevails in it . shows . _ From this point of view, no matter how well the teacher prepares for the lesson , his tactics and the methodology he uses do not serve to bring the cadets to a new step , because the foundations and requirements of authoritarian pedagogy have been introduced based on traditional educational technologies. ' lib, the conditions for the manifestation of individual and creative abilities have not been created. According to the analysis of creative-pedagogical literature , targeted education of creative abilities in cadets is appropriate for education that ensures the creation of a creative environment during the educational process .

References:

1. Umarov, IO (2021). AT THE MILITARY TRAINING CENTER TRAINING OF RESERVE AND RESERVE OFFICERS: TRADITIONS , INNOVATIONS , PROSPECTS. Oriental renaissance : Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(9), 939 -944.
2. Olimjonovich , U. I. (2022). THE MILITARY CAMPAIGN OF AMIR TIMUR TO THE GOLDEN HORDE IN 1391. INTERDISCIPLINARY IN UZBEKISTAN OF INNOVATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH, 1(11), 368-371.
3. Olimjonovich, UI (2022). THE SECOND J A HON URISHID A UZBEKISTAN S A NO A T CONSTRUCTION M A YDONCH A SIG A A YL A NICHE. CREATIVE TEACHER, 2(23), 193-197.

4. Olimjonovich , U. I. , Mirhokimovich , TA , & Ibrahimovich, A. I. (2022). ARMED FORCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Scientifi Impulse*, 1(4), 1884-1892.
5. Olimjonovich , U. I. , Mirhokimovich , TA , & Ibrahimovich, A. I. (2022). FREE AND PROSPEROUS LIFE. *CREATIVE TEACHER*, 2(24), 244-253.
6. Olimjonovich , U. I. , Rahmatali oglu, ES , Nurali oglu, JRS , Ikromjon oglu, IS , & Ahrorjon oglu, K. A. (2022). MILITARY KNOWLEDGE OF MILITARY PSYCHOLOGY IN THEIR COUNTRIESADVANTAGES AND IMPORTANCE. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(4), 415-419
7. Turdiboyev, S., & Abdurakhimov, I. (2021). COPYRIGHT IS THE FOUNDATION OF OUR DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 9(12), 1159-1160.
8. Kamoliddinovich, NM (2022). The Role of Military Pedagogy and Psychology in the Armed Forces. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 372-373.
9. Ogly, YAB, Ogly, AIN, & Abdulaev, A. (2021). The Main Directions of Military Patriotic Education. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 1(1), 99-100.
10. Yunusov, M. M., Sabirova, G. Kh., & Abdurakhimov, I. N. U. (2022). INFECTIOUS IX PROPHYLAXIS. *Science oath innovation* , 1(D 3), 87-88.
11. Salijanovna, IS, Sherbabayevna, HQ, Rahmanova, MY, Nabibullayevich, XF, & Son, AIN (2022). O SIB _ UPCOMING YOSH FOR A GENERATION EDUCATIONAL _ _ AND DIDACTIC O ' YINS THROUGH EDUCATION _ _ IN GIVING MODERN APPROACHES . *Science and innovation*, 1(B3), 18-22.
12. Takhir, T., Arabboy, Y., Zuhridin, G., & Abdurauf, G. (2022). Theoretical And Practical Pedagogical Bases of Formation of Professional Culture of Students of Military Education. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities* , 2 , 19-20.
13. Takhir, T., Arabboy, Y., Zuhridin, G., & Abdurauf, G. (2022). Theoretical And Practical Pedagogical Bases of Formation of Professional Culture of Students of Military Education. *Periodica J ournal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities* , 2 , 19-20.
14. Abdugafurovich, TT (2022). IN YOUNG PEOPLE HEALTHY IDEOLOGY AND PATRIOTISM THE FEELING FORMATION . *JOURNAL OF INTERDISCIPLINARY INNOVATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* , 1 (8), 846-849.
15. Abdugafurovich, TT (2021). The Importance of Forbidden Islam in Spiritual Growth, Problems and Solutions. *International Journal of Human Computing Studies* , 3 (1), 141-143.
16. Abdugafurovich , T. T. (2022). UPDATING UZBEKISTAN IN THEIR YOUTHS PATRIOTISM THE FEELING SHAPING . *CREATIVE TEACHER* , 2 (22), 444-446.
17. Abdugafurovich, TT (2021). In The Process of Educating Students of the Faculty of Military Education in the Spirit of Patriotism the Invaluable Contribution and Significance of the Uzbek People to the Victory Over Fascism (Dedicated to the 76th anniversary of The Victory of the Seco. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY* , 2 (4), 90-93.
18. Abdugafurovich, TT (2021). The importance of pedagogical ideas in the formation of youth. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* , 11 (4), 1066-1069.
19. Turgunbaev, T. A. (2021). Contribution and meaning of the Uzbek nation and victory over fascism *Molodoy uchenyy* , (18), 485-488.
20. Turgunbaev, T. A., & Karimov, O' U. (2020). EVERYTHING FOR THE FRONT, EVERYTHING FOR VICTORY ! *Internauka* , (19-4), 52-53.
21. Abdugafurovich, TT, & Shokhmukhammad, M. (2021). THE ROLE OF EDUCATING STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. *Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research* , 9 (9), 126-130.

22.Tahirjon, T. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF SPIRITUALITY AND PATRIOTISM IN THE MIND OF STUDENTS. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies , 2 (10), 299-304.

